

O'ZBEK YOZUVI TARAQQIYOT BOSQICHLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek yozuvining shakllanish va taraqqiyot bosqichlari to'g'risida so'z yuritilgan bo'lib, yozuvning to hozirgi ko'rinishga kelgunga qadar sodir bo'lgan o'zgarishlar, yozuvlarni o'zgartirish doirasida qabul qilingan qonunlar, o'zgarishlar natijasida amalga oshirilgan loyihalar haqida batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yozuv, alifbo, arab, kirill, lotin, xalqaro fonetik alifbo

Butun rivojlanish tarixi davomida o'zbek tilida uch xil yozuv mavjud edi. O'tgan asrning 20-yillari oxirigacha o'zbeklarning etnik guruhi arab alifbosiga asoslangan edi. Sovet hokimiyati paydo bo'lishi bilan yozuv bir qator islohotlarga duch keldi. So'ng 1938-yilgacha lotin alifbosi ishlatilgan, keyin esa kirill alifbosiga o'tilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasi mustaqil davlatga aylangandan so'ng 1993-yilda yana lotin alifbosi qaytarildi. Bugungi kunda o'zbek yozuvida arab harflari, lotin va kirill harflari parallel ravishda qo'llanilmoqda. Katta avlod kirill grafikasini afzal ko'radi, chet elda yashaydigan o'zbeklar esa arab harflariga o'rganishgan. Maktablarda o'quvchilar lotin tilida o'qishadi, shuning uchun o'quvchilar va o'quvchilarga sovet davrida nashr etilgan kitoblarni o'qish juda qiyin.

O'zbek tili fors tilidan olingan so'zlarga boy. XX asrda lug'at rus tilidagi so'zlar bilan sezilarli darajada boyitildi va bugungi kunda u ingliz tilidagi so'zlar bilan jadal ravishda to'ldirilmoqda. Davlat dasturiga muvofiq, o'zbek tilini boshqa tillardan olingan so'zlardan tozalash boshlangan. Bularning barchasi, shubhasiz, o'zbek tilini va tarjimalarini o'rganishda ba'zi bir qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi, ammo uni o'ziga xos va yanada qiziqarli qiladi. Tarixda o'zbek tilini yozish uchun ko'p alifbolar qo'llanilgan. 1928-yilgacha savodli kishilar o'zbek tilini arab yozuvida yozishgan. 1928-yildan 1940-yilgacha o'zbek tili lotin yozuvida yozilgan. 1940-yil Iosif Stalinning buyrug'i bilan majburan kirill yozuviga o'tilgan. 1992-yilgacha o'zbek tili shu yozuvda yozilgan. 1993-yil O'zbekiston rasman lotin yozuvini yana qaytadan kirgizdi. Hozirda O'zbekistonda ta'lim muassalarida lotin yozuvidan foydalaniladi. Shunday bo'lsa ham yoshi

kattalar va O'zbekiston tashqarisida yashaydigan o'zbeklar hali ham kirill yozuvidan foydalanishadi.

Alifbodagi o'zaro farqlar (Alifbodagi o'zaro farqlar)				
Arabcha (Arabcha)	Lotincha (Lotincha)	Kirillcha (Kirillcha)	Lotincha (Lotincha)	Xalqaro Fonetik Alifbosi (Xalqaro Fonetik Alifbosi)
1929	1936-1940	1940-1992	1992	
ا, ه	Ə ə	А а	A a	[a], [æ]
ب	B b	Б б	B b	[b]
د	D d	Д д	D d	[d]
ه	E e	Э э	E e	[e]
ف	F f	Ф ф	F f	[f]
گ	G g	Г г	G g	[gʲ]
ح, ه	H h	Х х	H h	[h]
ی	I i	И и	I i	[i]
چ, ژ	Ç ç, Z z	Ж ж	J j	[dʒ]
ك	K k	К к	K k	[kʲ]
ل	L l	Л л	L l	[l]
م	M m	М м	M m	[m]
ن	N n	Н н	N n	[n]
ا	A a	О о	O o	[ɔ]
پ	P p	П п	P p	[p]
ق	Q q	Қ қ	Q q	[q]
ر	R r	Р р	R r	[r]
ث, س, ص	S s	С с	S s	[s]
ت, ط	T t	Т т	T t	[t]
و	U u	У у	U u	[u]
و	V v	В в	V v	[v], [w]

خ	X x	X x	X x	[x]
ى	J j	Й й	Y y	[j]
ذ, ز, ض, ظ	З з	Z z	Z z	[z]
و	O o	Ў ў	O' o'	[o]
غ	Q q	F f	G' g'	[k]
ش	Ş ş	Ш ш	Sh sh	[ʃ]
چ	C c	Ч ч	Ch ch	[tʃ]
ع, ء	'	Ъ	'	[ʔ], [:]

Arab yozuvi

O'zbekistonda 1929-yilgacha arab yozuvidan foydalanilgan. 1920-yillarning o'rtalaridan O'zbekistonda arab yozuviga keng hujum boshlandi. Arab yozuvi qoloqligimizning, savodsizligimizning, dindorligimizning sababchisi deb e'lon qilindi. 1929-1930 o'quv yilidan O'zbekiston lotin yozuviga o'tdi va biz o'zbek xalqi asrlar davomida yaratilib kelingan hamda chop etilgan ilmiy, badiiy va falsafiy adabiyotdan uzilib qoldik.

Yanalif

1929-yildan boshlab arab yozuvidan yangi lotin vozuvi (yanalif)ga o'tilgan. U 1940-yilgacha ishlatilgan.

A a	B b	C c	Ç ç	D d	E e	Ə ə	F f
G g	Q q	H h	I i	J j	K k	L l	M m
N n	Ŋ, ŋ	O o	Ө ө	P p	Q q	R r	S s
Ş ş	T t	U u	V v	X x	Y y	Z z	Z z
	'						

Kirill yozuvi.

1940-yilda O'zbekistonda kirill yozuviga o'tildi. Buning natijasida 1929-1940-yillar oralig'ida chop etilgan ilmiy, badiiy, pedagogik, o'quv adabiyotlardan uzilib qoldik.

А а	Б б	В в	Г г	Д д	Е е	Ё ё	Ж ж
З з	И и	Й й	К к	Л л	М м	Н н	О о
П п	Р р	С с	Т т	У у	Ф ф	Х х	Ц ц
Ч ч	Ш ш	Ъ ъ	Ь ь	Э э	Ю ю	Я я	Ў ў
Қ қ	Ғ ғ	Ҳ ҳ					

1940-yildan 1991-yilgacha o'rta hisob bilan o'zbek tilida 50 ming nomda 50 million nusxada kitoblar chop etilganini (bunga shu yillari nashr etilgan jurnal, gazetalar kirmaydi) hisobga olsak, biz yana lotin yozuviga o'tishda qanchadan qancha adabiyotdan yiroqlashishimiz mumkinligi ayon bo'ladi.

Lotin yozuviga ko'chish

Lekin, dunyoning eng rivojlangan mamlakatlari (ularni sanab o'tirishning hojati yo'q) lotin yozuvidan foydalanadilar. Shuning uchun ham hozirgi eng zamonaviy texnika, tabiiy fanlar yoki ijtimoiy tadqiqotlar haqidagi adabiyotlar shu yozuv asosida yoritiladi. BMT, UNESCO va boshqa xalqaro tashkilotlarning xabar qilishlaricha, yangi texnika, texnologiya va fanga tegishli adabiyotlarning 80 foizi lotin yozuvida chop etilar ekan.

A a	B b	D d	E e	F f	G g	H h	I i
J j	K k	L l	M m	N n	O o	P p	Q q
R r	S s	T t	U u	V v	X x	Y y	Z z
O' o'	G' g'	Sh sh	Chch	ng	'		

Demak, O'zbekistonni dunyoning rivojlangan mamlakatlari qatoriga qo'shilishi uchun lotin yozuviga o'tish maqsadga muvofiqdir. O'zbekistonda bu jarayon bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirilmoqda.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи

таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnalı*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққийетининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og’ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

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²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

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